

First Report on CL and Nectar.

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1 Introduction:

The Context Programming paradigm as introduced in our previous work[1] has evolved since, in this paper, which serves a second report of the previous one, we will note and comment on improvements and regressions.

2 A Reminder of Nectar's λ -Execution:

As previously stated, we can express execution as a mathematical function:

$$\Theta(x) = \lambda x.(P(x)) \tag{1}$$

This function must have x defined in a program set \mathbb{P} in which it may not be contiguous.

3 The current implementation of Nectar:

The current implementation of Nectar allows the following syntax:

```
#include <GenericsLibrary/std.nhh>
```

```
const main()  
{  
    try {  
        pthread_exit();  
    }  
  
    return 0;  
}
```

In which this segment is completely separated from data. In order to access process data you would need a trait, such as *ThreadShared* to retrieve the current thread information.

```

#include <GenericsLibrary/std.nhh>

const main()
{
    try {
        let cur := ThreadShared->current_thread_;
        cur->exit();
    }

    return 0;
}

```

This could be represented logically as:

$$\text{Trait}(C) := \text{Rules}(C) \in \mathbb{P} \quad (2)$$

Such traits shall be valid in C & $\Theta(C)$. Notice that the definition has changed from C to \mathbb{P} . It is to express trait without a circularity condition in between.

4 Examples of programs written in Nectar:

4.1 A CUDA example in Nectar:

```

import cudaMalloc;

const main()
{
    let ptr := 0;
    let sz := 8;
    cudaMalloc(ptr, sz);
}

```

4.2 A Checked resource example in Nectar:

```

#include <GenericsLibrary/std.nhh>

const main()
{
    try {
        terminate();
    }

    return 0;
}

```

4.3 A simple program in Nectar:

```
extern exit;

const main()
{
    let _ := exit(0);
    if (_ == 0): {
        return 0;
    }
    return 0;
}
```

5 Motivations of Nectar:

The paper effectively tries to address underlying issues when designing Computer Systems in data separation. That is separation data and text in a Von-Neumann architecture. Examples includes: Operating System Kernels, Program Compilers, Program Linkers.

6 Applications of Nectar:

Nectar applies to systems programming, specifically in unprivileged and privileged code ran Natively by an Instruction Set Architecture.

7 Conclusion:

The conclusion of this report, although short, is improvements in understanding how data gets separated from code, clearer formulas, and a better idea on where to head from now on.